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The Social Media Uses to Marketing Development of Agricultural Products in Tempok Village, Tomposo District, Minahasa Regency

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Abstract

The agricultural sector plays an important role in the lives of Indonesian people and even the world. However, until now there are still many farmers in Indonesia whose lives are below the decent standard or are still poor. This is caused by one of the low selling prices of products experienced by farmers because of the long marketing chain. This situation was responded to by farmers in Tempok Village, Minahasa District by utilizing social media as a means of developing and marketing agricultural products using social media. The purpose of this study was to determine how social media is used to develop agricultural products in Tempok Village. This study is a descriptive study with a qualitative approach. The data sources used are primary and secondary data. Data analysis by conducting validity and reliability tests using qualitative data analysis techniques, the Miles and Huberman model. With the theoretical basis used for social media marketing, Digital Marketing, E-Commerce, Consumer Behavior, Social Media Marketing Activity. Based on the data analysis carried out, it was concluded that social media is beneficial for farmers in Tempok Village. Some of the benefits that are felt are, by using social media, it can cut the existing marketing chain. Farmers in Tempok Village, but farmers must also understand more efficient strategies in promoting agricultural products in the use of social media. Social media is also useful for cutting the existing marketing chain. In addition, with social media, the prices obtained by farmers are also higher because they no longer sell their products through fences or middlemen.

Keywords: Utilization, Farmers, Social Media, Marketing Chain

Introduction

Indonesia is a developing country that has abundant natural resources in it. Indonesia is also one of the countries in Southeast Asia that has large natural resources (SDA), especially in food sources. The food ingredients produced are the result of the agricultural sector which has an important role in the economic system in Indonesia. According to data provided by the official article belonging to the East Java provincial Ministry of Communication and Information, the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) reported that the value of agricultural exports in April 2022 experienced positive growth of 15.89% when compared to the same period in the same year last year. The growth that occurred was due to the large demand for commodities from large countries such as China and America. The Head of BPS, Margo Yuwono, said that the increase had reached 11.93% or with a total share of 1.66%. When viewed from the data provided by BPS, it can be said that Indonesia has made the agricultural sector one of the sectors that can develop the Indonesian economy.

The role of the agricultural sector in the development of the Indonesian economy includes as a producer of food, helping to create a source of labor in other economic sectors and can also be a source of foreign exchange for the country. The agricultural sector since the era of Soekarno's leadership to the current era of Jokowi's leadership, the agricultural sector has become one of the sectors that is able to support economic growth in Indonesia. We cannot deny that in the lives of people in Indonesia who are agrarian in nature. The agricultural sector in Indonesia is not only one of the sectors that is able to drive the existing economy, but can also provide various jobs, especially in rural areas. As is the case in the province of North Sulawesi which has a population of 2.6 million (2021) and 88.70% (2021) are farmers. According to data released by BPS, the results of the North Sulawesi NTP in November increased by 1.39%, but in December it decreased by 0.26%, this was due to the low selling price of agricultural products that would be received by farmers.

The low selling price of agricultural products is usually caused by multiple factors, a concrete example of which is the accumulation of perishable agricultural products that take up a lot of space, forcing farmers to immediately sell them to intermediary traders at prices that may be below the market price so that their products can sell. This results in farmers getting cheap prices from the long marketing chain. From previous research conducted by Choiriyah (2017) in the Bulukerto Village area, it was revealed that Bulukerto Village is very dependent on intermediary traders and has a marketing chain that Therefore, Choiriyah said that the only way that farmers in the village could take was to use or take advantage of existing technological advances.

Technology is systematic practical knowledge to increase the production of goods and services manifested in productive, organizational, or mechanical capabilities, based on scientific research or theory (Seattler, 2014). Since Covid spread in Asia, it has greatly influenced the development of technology, the results of the East Ventures Ventures Digital Competitiveness Index (EVDCI) 2021 study show that digital competitiveness between provinces in Indonesia is increasingly evenly distributed. This mapping can be seen from the increase in the median score of the digital competitiveness index (EV-DCI) from 27.9 in 2020 to 32.1 in 2021. This technological progress was experienced by farmers from Minahasa Regency, precisely in Tempok Village, Tompasso District, where the majority of the population are farmers. Data from BPS (2021) shows that in Minahasa

Regency there are 8,630 who work as farmers, that number includes those in Tempok Village. Similar to Bulukerto Village, both villages still have farmers who depend on middlemen and have a long marketing chain process. However, farmers are also trying to switch to social media so that they are no longer dependent on intermediary traders. As we know, in the era of the rise of internet technology like today, where everything is digital and online, it will definitely be very helpful in marketing through social media. It can be seen from internet penetration in Indonesia starting from the early period of 2021-2022, there are 210.03 million internet users in Indonesia.

From these data, we can conclude that this phenomenon shows that Indonesian people are very fond of using social media. It is undeniable that most Indonesian people make social media a part of their lifestyle and daily activities. In the data provided by M. Ivan Mahdi in DataIndonesia.id, it was stated that the use of social media in Indonesia had reached 191 million people in early January 2022. This number increased by 12.35% compared to the previous year. It was recorded based on a report from We Are Social, the number of active users of social media in Indonesia was 191 million in January 2022. This number is estimated to have increased by 12.35% compared to the previous year where the number of users in the previous year was 170 people. The agricultural sector does have great potential to drive economic growth in North Sulawesi Province (Sulut) to improve again after growing negatively by 3.89% in the first semester of 2020.

The Head of the North Sulawesi Agriculture Service in the Coffee Morning event themed "Together with the Media Building North Sulawesi Agriculture" which was held at the Manado Agricultural Quarantine office, said that "the regional government is determined to encourage the agricultural sector so that it continues to be able to produce higher production, including by utilizing modern agricultural technology, the Head of the North Sulawesi Agricultural Technology Assessment Center, Steivie Karouw also said that he would continue to innovate so that it becomes an alternative for farmers. In February, the 2022 Farmer Exchange Rate (NTP) in North Sulawesi increased by 0.67% to 110.91% compared to January which was still 110.17%. The improvement in the NTP was due to the speed of the increase in the Price Index received by Farmers (It) being higher than the Price Index received by Farmers (Ib) being higher than the Price Index paid by Farmers (Ib). It rose to 0.89%, while Ib only rose by 0.22%.

However, the data provided by BPS (Central Statistics Agency) in 2022 shows that the NTP (Farmer's Exchange Rate) data in October 2022 in the North Sulawesi region fell to 107.82. This decrease of 6 was due to the speed of the Price Index received by Farmers (It) being faster than the Price Index paid by farmers (Ib). It fell by 1.89%, while Ib fell by only 0.09%. NTP both YTD (calendar year) and YoY (year on year) showed a downward trend. Based on YTD it fell by 4.19%, and YoY 3.12%. The Agricultural Household Business Exchange Rate (NTUP) also decreased by 2.16%, from 106.69 in September to 104.38% in October. This study has several objectives: 1) Analyze the implementation of marketing strategies for the use of social media for marketing agricultural products in Tempok Village, Minahasa Regency; 2) Analyze and explain the effectiveness of the use of social media to increase agricultural output in Tempok Village, Tompasso District, Minahasa Regency.

Methodology

Data collection method is a technique or way that is done to collect the data that will be needed, where this method refers to a way so that its use can be shown through research

questionnaires, interviews, observations, tests, documentation, and so on. according to the type of research used by the researcher is a qualitative approach, then the data collection technique chosen by the researcher in this study is:

a) Interview, In this interview the researcher also uses writing instruments as notes to record the main points conveyed by the source, and is continued with more complete and detailed notes after the interview is completed. And besides that, in the interview session, in addition to using writing instruments, the researcher also uses a recording device to help the researcher get an accurate answer from the source.

b) Observation is an activity towards a process or object with the intention of feeling and then understanding knowledge that comes from a phenomenon based on previously adhered knowledge and ideas, to obtain information needed to continue a research. According to the definition of one of the experts quoted from the book *Introduction to Microteaching* (2020) by Uswatun Khasanah, Margono said that observation is a technique for seeing and observing various changes in social phenomena that continue to grow and develop;

c) Documentation To complete the data needed in this research, the documentation method is used as an aid and one of the supporting tools, where the documentation method in question is to find data on things or variables in the form of notes, transcripts, books, newspapers, magazines, inscriptions, meeting minutes, ledgers, agendas and so on. When compared to other methods, this method is not so difficult; d Hypothesis Formulating a research hypothesis is the third step in a study, where after the researcher has put forward the theoretical basis and framework of thought. Based on the formulation of the problem and the objectives of the research and the framework of thought that has been developed, a hypothesis can be formulated, namely that it is suspected that the development of social media for farmers in Tempok Village can have an impact on the level of agricultural production for farmers in the village.

Qualitative data analysis techniques have a process that is carried out since before entering the field, during the field, and after the field is finished. In this study using the qualitative data analysis technique of the Miles and Huberman model;

a) Data Reduction (Data Reduction) In the first analysis process that must be done in qualitative research using the Miles and Huberman Model is data reduction. In KBBI, the word reduction means reduction or cutting. In this study, data reduction is carried out to select data that has been obtained and then organized so that a comparison of various data obtained from various sources can be seen clearly and then presented well. Data reduction means that data must be streamlined, then selected which is important, then simplified, and then abstracted;

b) Data Presentation Data presentation is carried out in this study to be able to clearly see the facts that occur in the field which is the place of research. Qualitative research presents data not in the form of narrative text, because in that study the presentation of data in that form makes the data presented not well organized. Through data presentation, the data obtained can be organized and arranged in a relationship pattern so that it can be easier to understand;

c) Conclusion Drawing/Verification The third step in the qualitative data analysis process according to Miles and Huberman is drawing conclusions or verification. The

conclusions put forward at the beginning are still temporary, and change when new evidence is found that can support the next stage of data collection. The conclusions in this study are expected to be new findings that have never existed before. Where the findings are in the form of a description or picture of an object that was previously unclear, so that after being studied it becomes clear, in the form of a causal or interactive relationship, hypothesis or theory

Results and Discussion

The Tompaso District area has a northern border with the West Tompaso District, in the east with the North Kawangkoan Langowan District and the West Kakas District, in the south with the West Tompaso District and in the west with the West Tompaso District. Tompaso District itself is located in Minahasa Regency which is located between 1240 800 - 1240 820 East Longitude and 10 170 - 10 190 North Latitude, has an area of 28 km². The Tompaso District area has a northern border with the Kawangkoan District and the West Tompaso District, in the east with the West Kakas District, in the south with the West Tompaso District and in the west.

a. Benefits of Social Media in Saving Time and Energy

Farmers in Tempok Village this time revealed many benefits provided by social media. Some of the benefits felt by farmers in Tempok Village include the existence of this social media can be a new market, wide reach, unlimited time, and price. After using social media, farmers in Tempok Village revealed many benefits felt. Some expressions of the benefits of social media include wide reach, can be accessed 24 hours, higher prices are obtained, can find new markets, even make it easier when making sales. Farmers said with the many benefits felt, farmers prefer to make sales through social media, because through social media, farmers have price power and can act as price makers so that the prices obtained by farmers are much higher than through middlemen or traders. These many benefits have made farmers in Tempok Village start to change the sales system which was initially conventional through traders, now using social media. Prastuti (2013) in his previous research said that the benefit factor has a significant and positive influence on the adoption of social media.

Table 1. Interview Results on the Benefits of Using Social Media

Interview Topics	Sub	No.	Information
Benefits of Using Social Media		1	The benefits of social media are many, especially in finding new markets. Like through groups on Facebook, just post it, many people will see it, because the reach is wide.
		2	Selling using an online system is very helpful, because the reach is wide and there is a lot of time, and we don't need to meet to offer goods, just stay at home

		and post via Facebook or WhatsApp.
	3	There are many benefits to online sales, because the prices you get are also high because of direct communication with the buyer.
	4	The benefit is that if you want to sell your production results quickly you can get buyers at a high price.
	5	Get a buyer faster, then set a good price, because it is directly with the buyer, even if you bargain, it is still considered high and time is more efficient.
	6	Get a buyer faster, then set a good price, because it is directly with the buyer, even if you bargain, it is still considered high and time is more efficient.
	7	If asked about the benefits, there are many, especially for us, the farmer group, there are so many benefits, such as information about sales prices and plant price information, which is very helpful, 96 farmer groups here can get stable profits.
	8	We, the women farmers here, get a lot of benefits because we can help our husbands to get additional income by helping to sell agricultural products or we can help to get networks for plants whose selling prices are increasing or no longer decreasing.
	9	We young people are really helped by the existence of social media because with social media there are many things that we young farmers can get, such as plants that are currently on the rise in the market or types of good medicines. It can be said that social media provides a lot of information.
	10	We from the local government do see that social media has a positive impact because of its many benefits. Because through social media such as Facebook which is widely used by farmers to get information, such as prices on the market or to find consumers outside the province of North Sulawesi.

Source: Literature Reviews, 2024

Based on the data obtained in the study above, researchers can draw the conclusion that the benefits provided by social media, the adoption of social media will also be better. In this study it was also found that the higher the benefits of social media felt by farmers, the greater the intention to use social media. In addition, there are various benefits provided by social media in terms of selling agricultural products that have no time limits and the reach provided is also wide and can make time for farmers efficient. And not only that, in terms of their energy, it also becomes efficient. The work of farmers who are many makes them drain less energy. Because with social media even though they only stay at home and rest, they can still sell their products.

b. Benefits of Social Media in Creating New Business Opportunities

Based on the many benefits provided by the use of social media, many business opportunities are created. According to farmers in Tempok Village, there are indeed many business opportunities using social media. According to farmers in Tempok Village, the existence of social media has a very positive impact. Some of the positive impacts that are produced are the opening of new business opportunities, finding new consumers, and being able to enter new markets, and the most recent thing done by the people in Tempok Village is selling fried or roasted peanuts and foods such as banana chips and others.

Table 2. Interview Results on the Benefits of Social Media in Creating New Business Opportunities

Interview Sub Topics	No.	Information
Benefits of Social Media in Creating New Business Opportunities	1	The opportunities given are many, but it comes back to how the book can provide a sense of security and trust. Because the farmers here prioritize long-term relationships
	2	There are many opportunities, but the key to the success of this business is honesty, so first we must be honest in making purchases and sales so that we also gain the trust of others and establish good relationships in the future.
	3	There are many business opportunities, because as time goes by, business becomes more sophisticated and we also have to follow developments.
	4	There are indeed many business opportunities, but there are also many competitors, so you have to be smart and honesty is a priority when offering goods to consumers.
		The new business opportunities now are banana chips and roasted peanut sales. For example, usually you can only sell raw peanuts directly to consumers, now not only that, there are several areas that have ordered a lot of peanuts that are processed themselves
	6	Regarding opportunities, social media opens up many opportunities for farmers to sell their agricultural products outside the region.
	7	Social media does provide many opportunities, from our farmer group the opportunities we get are things like easy sales at very high prices, what's more, we can

		also share information with farmer groups outside the area.
	8	Talking about social media opportunities for mothers who are farmers, there are many, one of which is the opportunity to have a working relationship with mothers who are farmers in other areas.
	9	If we talk about business opportunities like ours, the biggest opportunities we get from the media right now are easy sales access and lots of consumer opportunities.
	10	If you say that the opportunities provided are very many, and if we look at the business opportunities from the government, we see that there are several new business opportunities, one of which is currently developing, namely peanuts.

Source: Literature Reviews, 2024

This is in line with what Sumijan (2013) said in his research that social media opportunities include the ability to reach more and can create higher efficiency. Based on these two things, with the impact of social media, farmers in Tempok Village are developing more of their business opportunities. Farmers who initially only had one sales system, namely through penada, now have many new sales systems. With this, the variety of products they sell is also greater and their agricultural business can also increase.

c. Benefits of Social Media Cutting the Marketing Chain

Based on observations from researchers and expressions given by farmers in Tempok Village, they often experience losses when selling their agricultural products to existing traders. The role of farmers is limited to price takers and can only accept the price decisions given by traders. However, with this social media, farmers have the option to sell to other consumers. With social media, it is also more profitable than selling through traders, because with social media the marketing chain becomes shorter so that the price obtained is high.

Table 3. Interview Results: The Benefits of Social Media in Cutting the Marketing Chain

Sub. Interview Topics	No.	Information
Benefits of Social Media Cutting the Marketing Chain	1	It is very profitable to use social media, because when selling on social media the price is different from the price when selling at the seller. Because sometimes there are naughty sellers, the price in the market goes up or is high but they don't want to buy at a high price
	2	It is profitable to use social media because it is sold

		directly to end users, besides cutting the marketing chain, we also have pricing power, if we sell through a marker, the payment system is in arrears so the money takes a long time to circulate.
	3	If the profit itself is good to use online because the price can be high, because this channel has cut a lot, if it goes through the penada it is too long, the penada is brought to the market and then taken to the port and so on too much. Transportation costs are too much, here it is only 5 thousand, in other places it can be up to 20 thousand. So if we use this online we can sell directly for 20 thousand
	4	The sales margin itself is still high on social media because the price is higher, but sometimes farmers still choose to go to the farmer because they do not have the capital to take care of the land.
	5	For expensive prices, use online, but sometimes the trader gives a loan of capital but with the condition that when the harvest is later sold to him. Well, as a farmer, sometimes you need capital, so you accept the offer from the trader.
	6	We farmers are helped in reselling our agricultural products to consumers, because it is fast and safe because it goes directly to consumers, so the profits we get are in accordance with what we farmers want.
	7	The benefits provided by social media are very helpful for farmer groups in gaining profits, because the desired sales are in accordance with what is expected because they sell directly to consumers, no longer needing to go through intermediaries.
	8	We mothers, if we sell our own agricultural products, make a lot of profit compared to if we sell them to traders, usually the price given is lower than the market price.
	9	For young farmers, it is indeed very helpful, because we are young people who want to sell agricultural products directly to consumers, so the profit is large because it is in accordance with the price in the market, if we go through a middleman, usually the profit obtained is small because of the costs that must be incurred.
	10	It is very helpful, because farmers can prosper with the profits they get. Indeed, if it goes through a receiver, the costs that farmers have to spend are indeed high, so having social media really helps farmers in Tempok Village in getting profits.

Source: Literature Reviews, 2024

Farmers in Tempok Village revealed how the benefits provided by social media greatly helped the farmers. The most dominant benefit felt from the use of social media is the higher prices obtained by farmers and the costs incurred are not so burdensome for

farmers and again the ease of information on sales prices is fast and easy to obtain. This is because the marketing chain has been cut a lot. Especially for farmer groups whose sales results must be shared with other members, with the existence of social media, the sales obtained are high and the sales profit sharing process is also even. With the existence of social media, farmers in Tempok Village can use level 0 (zero) channels where sales are made to end consumers and not through other intermediaries. Farmers in Tempok Village also revealed that their profit turnover increased by selling conventionally. Likewise, the opinion given by the local government that with the existence of social media, the income of farmers in Tempok Village increased as well as the welfare of farmers increased.

Conclusion

From the results and discussions that have been presented, several conclusions can be drawn regarding the benefits of social media for farmers in Tempok Village. It has a significant influence on the development of agricultural products in Tempok Village, but farmers must also better understand more efficient strategies in promoting agricultural products in the use of social media. Social media is also useful for cutting the existing marketing chain. Farmers in Tempok Village who initially always experienced problems related to long marketing chains and many intermediaries, with this social media, farmers in Tempok Village can sell directly to end consumers. In addition, with this social media, farmers in Tempok Village also get a higher price, if through middlemen it is only Rp. 5000, through social media farmers in Tempok Village can get a price of Rp. 20,000.

Suggestion

Based on the phenomenon that occurred in Tempok Village, it can be suggested that farmers in Tempok Village share information related to the use of social media for marketing agricultural products to other farmers around Tompaso District so that the agricultural sector in Tompaso District can progress further in the future. In addition, farmers in Tempok Village must also be more creative in utilizing social media, not only selling agricultural products such as fruits, vegetables or flowers, but in the future the variety of products they sell must increase such as fertilizers and seeds. This is so that farmers in Tempok Village are not inferior to other farmers throughout Indonesia because by using this social media the reach is wider and competitors can also come from anywhere

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